

[Title] A method to design correct token incentive mechanism towards well-functioned blockchain platform/application. [Short Description] A token is one of the most important feature of blockchain. It can financially incentivise people to behave as your system intends. However incorrect token incentive design may lead to the destruction of a system. In this session, I introduce the method to design correct token incentive while referring to Galleon project which aims to create decentralized review platform. [Biography] Doctoral student in Osaka University, Japan, studying blockchain and its integrations. Also Co-founder at Galleon Foundation which aims to create decentralized review platform. The former CTO at LastRoots which was successful with ICO and raised about 6M USD. Blockchain engineer, research and evangelist.